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EVALUATION OF IN VIVO NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF ROOT OF CLITORIA TERNATIA AGAINST ETHIDIUM BROMIDE INDUCED DEMYELINATION RAT MODEL.

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ABSTRACT

Clitoria ternatea root is widely used in neuralgia for traditional and herbal medicine. In this study we evaluate the therapeutic strategies to accelerate the reconstruction of lost myelin sheath. The Methanolic root extract of *Clitoria ternatea* was tested at 100mg/kg and 200mg/kg when administered orally for a period of 28 days after induction demyelination in wistar rats by giving intra cranial injection of ethidium bromide at a dose of 1µg/0.03ml of PBS/kg body weight. The efficacy was expressed in terms of behavioural studies were observed on 1st, 2nd and 4th week. After 28 days the animals were sacrificed and brain tissue was subjected to histopathological and biochemical studies. The result from behavioural, histopathological and biochemical studies suggested that the Methanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root have potential protective effect on the ethidium bromide induced demyelination on wistar rats by intra cranial administration. In the pharmacological evaluation of methanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root for their protective effect on demyelinated motor neuron diseases.

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INTRODUCTION

Axonal myelination in the vertebrate central nervous system is pivotal for saltatory nerve impulses, whereas demyelination can construct serious diseases such as multiple sclerosis (MS) (1). MS is recognized as an autoimmune, inflammatory, demyelinating and Neurodegenerative disease of the central nervous system affecting over 2 million people worldwide (2). It is characterized by a progressive clinical decline due to axonal loss from chronic demyelination (3). Nowadays it is widely accepted that cognitive dysfunction occurs in 40-70% of MS patients (4). The most common cognitive deficits are memory dysfunction and spatial perception impairment (5, 6). Recent studies, especially using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) technique, has indicated that structural derangements of both the cerebral cortex and the hippocampus (a principle locus of memory consolidation) take place in patients with MS (7,8). Although different mechanisms may contribute to the demyelination and neurodegeneration in MS, it became clear in recent years that oxidative stress plays the key role in the process (9, 10). Toxic demyelination by ethidium bromide (EB) is one of the most commonly used models for analyzing the cellular changes that occur during demyelinating pathologies such as MS (7). Direct injection of EB induces focal demyelinating lesions at the site of injection by selectively damaging oligodendrocytes and astrocytes, and consequently interfering with the demyelination and remyelination processes (7, 13). Previous studies have indicated the increase in oxidative stress following EB injection in different areas of the brain (11, 14).

Clitoria ternatea Linn. is an attractive perennial climber with conspicuous blue or white flowers. It belongs to the family Fabaceae and commonly known as “butterfly pea” and “shankhapuspi”. It is traditionally used to treat various ailments (15). The plant is native to south-east Asia and distributed in tropical Asia including India, the Philippines and Madagascar (16). Roots, seeds and leaves of *C. ternatea* are commonly used in the Ayurvedic system of medicine. Extracts of his plant have been used as an ingredient in the Ayurvedic 'Medhya Rasayana' as a rejuvenating recipe used for treatment of neurological disorders and are considered to enhance the intellect (17). Medicinal plants are very important in identifying new sources of therapeutical and industrial importance. Phytochemical analysis of methanol extract of confirmed the presence of tannins and resins and certain other constituents. The present study deals with the phytochemical analysis of the whole plant and seed extracts are used for stomatitis, piles, sterility in females, hematemeses, insomnia, epilepsy, psychosis, eucorrhoea and polyurea (18). The roots are bitter, laxative, intellect-promoting, diuretic, anthelmintic, tonic and are useful in dementia, hemicranias, burning sensations, leprosy, inflammation, leucoderma, bronchitis, asthma, pulmonary tuberculosis, ascites, fever, otalgia, he and as a cathartic Nadakarnik flower are also used for the treatment of snake bite and scorpion sting. *C. ternatea* has been shown to have number of pharmacological activities such as possessing anxiolytic antidepressant, anticonvulsant, anti stress (19), sedative, antipyretic, anti inflammatory, analgesic (20), Anthelmintic and antimicrobial activities. The extract of *C. ternatea* has been shown to improve learning ability, enhance memory, and increase apical and basal dendritic branches, and increase acetylcholine content and acetyl cholinesterase activity in rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals:

Adult male and female Wistar rats weighing 200 -250 g were housed in standard hygienic plastic cages (four in each) Under a 12 h light/dark cycle (lights on at 07:00 a.m.) in a room with controlled temperature (23 ± 2 °C). Food and water were available *ad libitum*. The experiments were carried out during the light phase of the cycle. All animal procedures were performed according to the National Institutes of Health: Guide for the care and use of laboratory animals. Efforts were made to minimize the number of animals used and their suffering.

Experimental phytochemistry

Plant material and extraction:

Clitoria ternatea root were purchased from local market in The Nilgiris, Ooty. The *Clitoria ternatea* root was authenticated at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore. The voucher specimen number is F-197.

Reagents and chemicals:

All the reagents, chemicals and solvents used for the experiments were of analytical grade and obtained from Sigma Aldrich (USA).

Extraction methodology:

Clitoria ternatea root was dried at 40 °C for 48 hours in hot air oven. Dried seeds were powdered using an electric mixer (Remi). Soxhlet extraction technique was used to prepare petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, methanol and aqueous extracts. Extraction was carried for 18 hours at a temperature not exceeding the boiling point of the solvents. The extracts were filtered using Whatmann filter paper (No.1), concentrated in vacuum under reduced pressure using rotary flask evaporator, and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The extracts were stored in amber colored bottles at 2-4 °C until further use. The petroleum ether extract was chilled in refrigerator until the use.

Experimental Pharmacology

Animals:

Adult male and female Wistar rats weighing 200 -250 g were housed in standard hygienic plastic cages (four in each) Under a 12 h light/dark cycle (lights on at 07:00 a.m.) in a room with controlled temperature (23 ± 2 °C). Food and water were available *ad libitum*. The experiments were carried out during the light phase of the cycle. All animal procedures were performed according to the National Institutes of Health: Guide for the care and use of laboratory animals. Efforts were made to minimize the number of animals used and their suffering.

Protocol for the evaluation of pharmacological activity:

Wistar rats of both sexes (12 weeks old, weight 200–250 g) will be housed under standard conditions in a temperature-controlled environment (23 °C \pm 2 °C) and a 12 h light/dark cycle the rats are then allocated into dietary regimens by feeding with the rat pellet supplied by Hindustan levers Ltd., Bangalore. After the 2 weeks of dietary manipulation, the animals were randomly divided into groups Animals were deeply anaesthetised with intraperitoneal injection of Ketamine (100mg/kg) and xylazine (20mg /kg) the rats are placed on the rat stereotaxic instrument in the skull- flat position. Hair of the skull surface was shaved and then an incision is made to expose the rat skull two holes are drilled in the skull according to appropriate coordinates. Two guide cannulae are inserted into the holes and fixed using dental cement after surgery dummy inner cannulae are inserted into the guide cannulae and left in the place and till the injections are made by Hamilton syringe. All animals are allowed to recover for one week before starting the microinjections Experimental model of MS is induced bilaterally by direct single injection of 3 μ l of 0.01% Ethidium bromide in sterile 0.9% saline. After the demyelination the animals are treated with the extracts and are observed for their behavioral studies after 28 days the animals were sacrificed and subjected for histopathology and biochemical analysis. The proposed experiment was approved by IAEC, Proposed No. JSSCP/IAEC/PH.D/PH.COG/03/2016-2017 JSS University and Mysore.

Grouping of animals:

The experimental design of the study was carried out in five groups with five Albino Wistar rats of both sexes (200-250gms) in each group.

(I) Group G₀ - Served as solvent control, received only 0.3%CMC (2ml) orally and daily **(II) Group G₁** - Received Ethidium bromide (EB) 1 μ g/ kg body weight in 0.03ml PBS (sterile) intra cerebrally.

(III) Group G₂- Received EB and standard drug for MS (Fingolimod) 100mg/kg body weight in 0.3% CMC orally and daily.

(IV) Group G₃ - Received EB and dried Methanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root 100mg/kg body weight in 0.3% CMC orally and daily.

(V) Group G₄ - Received EB and dried Methanolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root 200mg/kg body weight in 0.3% CMC orally and daily.

Behavioural pharmacology studies

Open field exploratory behaviour test:

This test has been utilized for behavioral changes in rats by exposing the animals to a novel environment and has been used to detect anxiogenic and anxiolytic activity under identical situation. A typical apparatus suitable for rats, comprises of large black area (96×96cm)with wall height (96cm). The floor was divided into 16 squares by white lines and the apparatus was placed in a dim light room. Mice were placed individually at one corner of the apparatus and were observed, thereafter for the next 10-15 minutes. The parameters noted were:

- (i) Ambulation (no. of squares crossed)
- (ii) Freeze (periods of immobility)
- (iii) Rearing (no. of times animal stand on its rear paws)
- (iv) Defecation (no. of fecal pellets).

Grip strength:

The test is being used to assess muscular strength or neuromuscular function in rats which can be influenced not only by sedative drug and muscle relaxant compounds but also by toxic agents. The method was discovered as 'test de 1' gripment' by Boissler and Simon (1960). Male or female rats were posed to a horizontal thin thread or metallic wire suspended about 10 cm in the air, which they immediately grasp with the fore limbs. Normal animals were able to catch the wire with hind limb and climb up within 5 seconds. The animals that are not able to touch the wire are considered as impaired.

Rota rod test:

The test is used to evaluate the activity of drugs interfering with motor coordination. The apparatus consists of horizontal metal rod of 3 cm diameter attached to a motor with the speed 20-25 revolution per minute. The rod is divided into five sections with wooden compartment, it allows simultaneous testing of 5 rats, the rod is in height of 50 cm above the table top in order to discourage the animal from falling off. The compartment made with wooden cardboard to restrict escape of animals when they fall from the rod, the test animals were tested for the time of falling from the roller.

Beam walks Test:

The test is used to evaluate the ability of animals to walk on beam. The apparatus consists of a horizontal metal rod of 1 cm diameter supported by two side stands of 30 cm height and animals are kept in the centre of the rod to allow walking on the beam. The parameters evaluated are faecal pellets, distance walk, time of immobility and falling time.

Biochemical parameters:

After completion of behavioural study the animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation for biochemical study. The whole brain was immediately dissected out, washed in normal ice cold saline and immediately cerebral cortex and midbrain was separated and processed for various biochemical estimation.

Evaluation of antioxidant activity

Malondialdehyde (MDA):

Lipid peroxidation was assayed by measuring the level of Malondialdehyde (MDA) in the brain tissues. Malondialdehyde was determined by measuring thio barbituric reactive species using the method of Ruiz-Larrea et al.(1994) in which the thio barbituric acid reactive substances react with thio barbituric acid to produce a red colored complex having peak absorbance at 532 nm.

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD):

SOD activity was assayed according to the method of Winter bourn et al. (1975). Enzyme activity is expressed as units per milligram of protein. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) is added to keep the solution from forming precipitates when bathos cuproine disulfonic acid (BCS) is added. BCS (an electron chain-associated free radical production inhibitor) and diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DETAPAC) are both added to inhibit iron-associated redox cycling and free radical production. Various amounts of protein are added into tubes until maximum inhibition of NBT reduction. Colored complex having peak absorbance at 532 nm was observed.

Histopathological studies:

Histopathological study was done according to (Bancroft *et al*, 1996) method. Tissue from mid brain and cerebral cortex were separated and fixed in 10 per cent formalin and were processed by conventional method, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 4-5 μ M and stained by heamotoxylin and eosin. Tissues were examined under a light microscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The animal tests were carried out to assess the induction and to evaluate the remyelination in animals. The tests are,

- Open field exploratory behavior test
- Rota rod test
- Grip strength test
- Beam walk test

The animals subjected for the above tests were observed for four weeks. The results obtained are as follows:

Fig 1: Showing % decrease in ambulation and difference in freezing time in open field test.

Fig 2: Showing the % difference in falling time in Rota rod test.

Fig 3: Shwoing % difference in time taken to catch the wire and % falling time in grip strength test.

Fig 4: Showing % difference in distance walk and falling time in beam walk test.

Biochemistry

4. Antioxidany activity

4.1. Malondialdehyde (MDA)

Table 1: Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extract on the concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA).

S.No	Sample Name	Concentration	nmol/gm/tissue
1	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> root methanolic extract	Saline	25±1.06
		Ethidium Bromide	40±1.53
		Extract 100mg	32±0.89
		Extract 200mg	26±1.12

Fig.5. Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extract on the concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the cortex of rats subjected to in-tracerebral injection of ethidium bromide.**Table 2: Effect of Fingolimod on the concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA). (Fingolimod ,Standard):**

S. No	Sample Name	Concentration	nmol/gm/tissue
2	Fingolimod	Saline	25±1.06
		Ethidium Bromide	40±1.53
		Extract 100 mg	25±1.23
		Extract 200 mg	18±1.02

Figure 6: Effect of Fingolimod on the concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the cortex of rats subjected to in-tracerebral injection of ethidium bromide.

4. 2. Superoxide dismutase

Table 3: Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extraction of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD).

S. No	Sample Name	Concentration	mg/tissue
1	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> root methanolic extract	Saline	30±0.99
		Ethidium Bromide	48±1.23
		Extract 100mg	45±1.56
		Extract 200mg	34±1.29

Fig.7. Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extraction of Superoxide Dismutase (SOD).

Table 4: Effect of Fingolimod on Superoxide Dismutase (SOD).

S. No	Sample Name	Concentration	mg/tissue
2	Fingolimod	Saline	30±0.96
		Ethidium Bromide	48±1.15
		Extract 100 mg	32±1.06
		Extract 200 mg	24±1.24

Figure 8: Effect of Fingolimod concentration on Superoxide Dismutase (SOD).

Evaluation Inflammatory activity

TNF- α and IL-6 were quantified according to the guidelines using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay kit. These particular assay kits were selected because of their high degree of sensitivity, specificity, inter- and intraassay precision and small amount of tissue sample required conducting the assay.

Table 5: Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extract on TNF – α .

S.No	Sample Name	Concentration	Pg/ml
1	<i>Clitoriaternatea</i> root methanolic extract	Saline	14.5±0.098
		Ethidium Bromide	19.9±0.126
		Extract 100 mg	13.8±0.106
		Extract 200 mg	11.4±0.21

Figure 9: Effect of *Clitoriaternatea* root methanolic extract on TNF – α .**Table 6: Effect of Fingolimodon on TNF – α (Fingolimod, Standard).**

S. No	Sample Name	Concentration	Pg/ml
2	Fingolimod	Saline	14.5±0.098
		Ethidium Bromide	19.9±0.126
		Extract 100 mg	12.5±0.102
		Extract 200 mg	10.6±0.114

Figure 10: Effect of Fingolimodon the concentration on TNF – α .**Table 7: Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extract on IL-6.**

S.No	Sample Name	Concentration	Pg/ml
1	<i>Clitoriaternatea</i> root methanolic extract	Saline	23.7±0.145
		Ethidium Bromide	36.9±0.106
		Extract 100 mg	31.4±0.958
		Extract 200 mg	26.9±1.04

Figure 11: Effect of *Clitoria ternatea* root methanolic extract on IL-6.

Table 7: Effect of Fingolimod on IL-6 (Fingolimod , Standard):

S.No	Sample Name	Concentration	Pg/ml
8	Fingolimod	Saline	23.7±0.145
		Ethidium Bromide	36.9±0.106
		Extract 100 mg	20.4±0.114
		Extract 200 mg	15.2±0.956

Figure 12: Effect of Fingolimod on the concentration on IL-6.

Histopathological studies

Table 12: Microscopic Examination.

BRAIN					
Microscopic features	Group 0	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV
HIPPOCAMPAL AREA					
1. NEURONS :-					
(a) Vacuolar degeneration	-	+	-	-	-
ecrosis	-	+	+	-	-
ominence in Substantia nigra	Well seen	Less prominent	+	+	++
2. GLIOSIS :-					
Astrocytes	+	++	+	+	+
ligodentrogial cells	-	+	-	-	-
3. CONGESTION :-					
(a)Brain Parenchymal vessels	+	++	+	+	+
horoid plexus	-	+	-	+	-

Conclusion: Group IV shows protective effect when compared with standard.

A. Solvent control group

(B) Induction Group.

(C) Standard Group (Fingolimod)

(D) *Clitoria ternatea* root extract 100mg/kg.

(E) *Clitoria ternatea* root extract 200 mg/kg.

Our present study has been carried out with a view to determine the pharmacological evaluation of their activity the *Clitoria ternatea* root has been used traditionally for various nervous disorders and brain tonic. Because of this reason this plant has been selected to evaluate scientifically the protective effect of the seeds on ethidium bromide induced demyelination. Here the Methonolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root used to evaluation of the protective effect on ethidium bromide induced demyelination in wistar rats by compared with standard drug.

Mostly demyelination of CNS produces deficit in locomotor and behavioral pattern. Symptoms are confusion, muscle weakness, numbness, muscle disco ordination and hind limb paralysis. Hence the following animal's tests were carried out to assess the induction and to evaluate the remyelination in animals. The tests are:

- Open field exploratory behavior test
- Rota rod test
- Beam walk test
- Grip strength test.

The animals subjected for above tests were observed for four weeks except the open field exploratory behavior test, which was carried out for only one week. The brain tissue of two animals in each group was subjected for biochemical and histopathological study.

In the present study histopathological lesions were observed in mice brain by exposing to the Methonolic root extract of *Clitoria ternatea* (100&200 mg/kg) at repeated dose during 28days exposure. Various pathological changes like necrosis and cellular degenerative with massive diffuse cells and changes have been observed in experimental mice brain in plant extract treated rats compared to control. The present investigation with severity of histopathological lesions indicates that the repeated exposure to plant extracts cause deleterious effects and making less fit for better survival. Our results are in consistent with similar to necrotic lesion observed following exposure to certain toxic substance such as ethidium bromide. Similar study on histopathological changes in animals by heavy metals has been reported earlier by several workers (Kumar and Pant, 1981; Akhilender Naidu, 1982; Usha Rani, 1986). The present results are in agreement with the results of (Savory and Garruto 1998; Vogelbruch et al, 2000) with neuronal degeneration and neurodegenerative diseases associated with aluminum. The cerebral cortexes are the key structures of memory formation. In the present study the brains tissue of experimental animal showed changes in histo architecture and necrosis in cerebral cortex and in mid brain compared to control which are form of neuro-degeneration. Similar result was reported by (Buraimoh, et al, 2011) with accumulation of Aluminium in the brain regions. Evidence of mild lesions in parts of the brain indicates the ability of the extract to cross the blood-brain barrier. In this study, pre treatment with plant extract, produced a reversal trend in most of the negative effects of behavior and showing protection in the brain tissue from pathological lesion with absence of necrosis and cellular Lipid peroxidation and SOD are related with cellular injury and is commonly used as an indicator of oxidative damage in cells and tissues and it is regarded as one of the primary key events in cellular damage. With increased LPO and SOD in myocardial homogenate of Isoproterenol administered rats.

CONCLUSION

In the pharmacological evaluation of selected Methonolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root for their protective effect in ethidium bromide induced demyelination on rats result in improvement in muscle strength and muscle coordination, thus proving the protective effect of this plant in motor neuron diseases by comparison with standard anti MS drug (Fingolimod). The components present in the seeds may be having the neutralization effect on ethidium bromide.

In the biochemical and histopathological study, it's observed that only 200mg/kg dose is showing the protective effect, which is not in agreement with the findings of the behavioral study. From the result s, it is found that the Methonolic extract of *Clitoria ternatea* root are useful in nervous diseases (demyelination diseases) by compared with standard drug.

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